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Firm Efficiency?
Evidence from Developing Countries**

**Bao-We-Wal BAMBE
Jean-Louis COMBES
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Does Environmental Policy Stringency Foster Firm Efficiency? Evidence from Developing Countries

Bao-We-Wal BAMBE¹ • Jean-Louis COMBES¹ • Ben-Vieira KOUASSI¹ • Sonia SCHWARTZ¹

¹UNIVERSITÉ CLERMONT AUVERGNE, UNIVERSITÉ D'ORLÉANS, LEO, 45067, ORLÉANS, FRANCE

Abstract

The claim that well-designed environmental policies can improve firm performance is well documented in the literature, but so far little research has focused on developing countries. This article therefore contributes to the existing literature by examining the impact of environmental stringency on firm efficiency in developing countries. Using a panel of 68 countries over the period 2006-2020, we combine the newly published Environmental Performance Index (EPI) as an indicator of the stringency of environmental regulations with firm-level data from the World Bank Enterprise Surveys (WBES) database. Our findings indicate that a tightening of environmental policies significantly increases firm efficiency, and that the effect is robust. Moreover, we find that the intensity of environmental stringency matters. Likewise, firm size, institutional quality, and firm pollution intensity also influence the relationship between environmental stringency and efficiency. Our results are important since they support the Porter hypothesis in the case of developing countries.

Keywords: • Environmental policy stringency • Firm efficiency • Developing countries

JEL Classification: Q55, Q58

Corresponding author: Ben-Vieira KOUASSI (B-Vieira_Demerel.KOUASSI@doctorant.uca.fr)

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“Pollution is a manifestation of economic waste and involves unnecessary or incomplete utilization of resources [...]. Reducing pollution is often coincident with improving productivity with which resources are used.”

Porter and Van der Linde (1995)

1 Introduction

The standard neoclassical framework considers that stringent environmental policies lead firms to use additional resources to reduce their levels of pollution, resulting in higher production costs and lower profits.¹ This traditional paradigm has been challenged by Porter (1991), who argues that greater environmental stringency may lead firms to adopt more innovative production methods, which may increase — rather than reduce — productivity, profitability, and competitiveness. In other words, Porter supports the idea that strict but well-designed environmental regulations can generate social benefits by reducing environmental damage and private benefits for the firms that are subject to them. Since the 1990s, what has since become known as the Porter hypothesis has received considerable attention in the literature, with rather mixed results (e.g., see Jaffe and Palmer, 1997; Berman and Bui, 2001; Chintrakarn, 2008; Fleishman et al., 2009; Lundgren and Marklund, 2010; Broberg et al., 2010; Broberg et al., 2013; Rubashkina et al., 2015; Albrizio et al., 2017; Martínez-Zarzoso et al., 2019). So far, most studies examining the impact of environmental regulations on firm performance have focused exclusively on developed countries. This is due in part to the difficulty of measuring environmental policy stringency accurately in developing countries, and in a way that allows for international comparisons among countries. Indeed, in recent years, developing countries have been implementing environmental policies aimed at reducing their impact on pollution and biodiversity, in order to address the environmental challenges they face. In this context, they are opting for green industrial policies, i.e., those that consider environmental issues. As a result, several agreements, treaties, and environmental policies are being implemented to achieve sustainable economic development. Therefore,

¹Environmental stringency can be defined as the extent to which environmental policies impose an explicit or implicit price on environmentally damaging behavior, e.g., the use of certain pollutants, greenhouse gas emissions, waste production, etc.

in line with the existing literature, one may wonder to what extent such policies, i.e., environmental policies, contribute to shaping firm outcomes in these countries.

Although a few papers have examined the Porter hypothesis in Asian or Latin American countries (e.g., see [Alpay et al., 2002](#); [Murty and Kumar, 2003](#); [Zhao et al., 2018](#); [Huang and Liu, 2019](#)), to the best of our knowledge, comprehensive studies covering a wide range of developing countries remain scarce or lacking. Against this background, this paper contributes to the existing literature, by examining the impact of environmental stringency on firm performance in developing countries. First, we use the newly published Environmental Performance Index (EPI) as an indicator of the stringency of environmental regulations. The EPI offers the possibility of measuring the stringency of environmental regulations for a large panel of countries, while addressing the multidimensional nature of environmental policies. Second, to the best of our knowledge, we are the first to test the Porter hypothesis on a large sample of developing countries. Firm-level data are extracted from the World Bank Enterprise Surveys (WBES) database. Our dependent variable, technical efficiency, is estimated from a Stochastic Frontier Analysis (SFA) referring to [Kumbhakar et al. \(2015\)](#), which takes into account unobserved heterogeneity across units and provides a further decomposition of inefficiency, distinguishing between persistent and transitory inefficiency.

Using a panel of 68 developing countries over the period 2006-2020, our findings suggest that a tightening of environmental policies significantly improves firm efficiency and that the effects are robust and economically significant. We also find that environmental policy stringency increases factor productivity and promotes the adoption of new or improved production methods. Next, we conduct a series of heterogeneity analyses and highlight some additional results. First, environmental policies do not have a significant effect on firm efficiency for low levels of environmental stringency, the effect becomes significant from the second quartile — around 32% — with the highest efficiency for levels of environmental stringency between the second and third quartiles, i.e., approximately between 32% and 36%. Second, for small firms, the positive effect of environmental stringency is slightly attenuated, while it is slightly amplified for medium-sized firms. Third, institutional quality amplifies the beneficial effect of environmental stringency on firm efficiency. Finally, our data also suggest that environmental stringency increases

greater efficiency for pollution-intensive firms.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. The next section discusses the theoretical framework. Section 3 presents the conceptual framework and methodology for measuring firm efficiency. Section 4 presents the data. The methodology is described in Section 5. Sections 6 and 7 present our main findings and provide sensitivity analyses, respectively. The last section concludes.

2 Background

Subsections 2.1 and 2.2 briefly discuss environmental policies in developing countries and review the empirical literature on the Porter hypothesis, respectively.

2.1 Environmental policies in developing countries

Developing countries are facing major environmental degradation, which seriously jeopardizes their long-term development. The high level of poverty, population growth, and limited resources, lead some populations to engage in many activities that are unsustainable in the long run and harmful to the environment, often irreparably (Walter and Ugelow, 1979; Bell and Russell, 2002). Although economic theories dealing with environmental issues are well documented in the literature (based on the experience of developed countries), the implementation process for environmental policies in the developing world remains complex and is shaped by multiple factors, such as inadequate funding, insufficient training of staff, weak enforcement mechanisms, and conflicting interests among stakeholders (De Oliveira, 2002, Rossouw and Wiseman, 2004, Ajulor, 2018). Even so, in recent years, developing countries have become aware of the importance of the environmental problems they face, and many have demonstrated their commitment to implementing policies aimed at reducing pollution and their impact on biodiversity.

Despite the obstacles developing countries face in tightening their environmental regulations, there are some examples of successful policies. For instance, in Mexico, a pollution tax was introduced in 1989, charging companies according to the amount of

greenhouse gas houses they generate. The tax was expanded in 1994 to include more pollutants, and by 1997 it was estimated to have reduced sulfur dioxide emissions by 45%. Likewise, Rwanda introduced a national ban on single-use plastic bags in 2008, which has been successful in reducing plastic pollution ([Pilgrim, 2016](#)). In addition, Rwanda is the first African country to reach an agreement with the International Monetary Fund (IMF) on Resilience and Sustainability Trust (RST) support to ensure sustainable growth. In South Africa, the government has implemented a series of environmental programs, including the National Environmental Management Act and the National Water Act, which have helped regulate pollution and protect natural resources ([Tshehla and Wright, 2019](#)). The country has also made progress in expanding its renewable energy sector, with the goal of producing 18 gigawatts of renewable energy by 2030 ([Winkler, 2005](#)).

2.2 Environmental regulations and firm performance

Although a large literature discusses the Porter hypothesis, the empirical evidence is not so clear-cut. [Jaffe and Palmer \(1997\)](#), among the pioneering studies on the issue, have empirically assessed the relationship between the stringency of environmental regulations and firm performance, captured by technological innovation. Using the Pollution Abatement Costs and Expenditure Survey for a panel of manufacturing industries in the United States, the authors find that environmental compliance expenditures have a positive effect on firm investment in research and development. Similarly, looking at the case of oil refineries in the Los Angeles air zone, [Berman and Bui \(2001\)](#) show that the regulations implemented to reduce pollution have improved firm productivity. [Lanoie et al. \(2011\)](#) have tested different versions of the Porter hypothesis on about 4,200 facilities in seven OECD countries. To capture environmental stringency, the authors conducted a survey in OECD countries to gauge perceptions regarding the stringency of environmental policies in each respective country. They argue that a stricter environmental policy provides an incentive for firms to become more innovative, by encouraging them to look for optimal ways to reduce their impact on the environment. Similar evidence is provided for the manufacturing sector in Quebec ([Lanoie et al., 2008](#)) or for European countries ([Rubashkina et al., 2015](#)).

In contrast to the studies mentioned above, other authors have found no support for the Porter hypothesis or have reported mixed results (for instance, see [Palmer et al., 1995](#); [Chintrakarn, 2008](#); [Fleishman et al., 2009](#); [Lundgren and Marklund, 2010](#); [Broberg et al., 2010](#); [Broberg et al., 2013](#)). Along the same lines, [Lanoie et al. \(2008\)](#) find contrasting results depending on the firm's level of pollution, or on the level of exposure to external competition. According to [Brännlund \(2008\)](#), there may be no effect, or it may depend on the way the environmental variable is measured, or on a lagged effect of environmental policy, as suggested by [Broberg et al. \(2013\)](#). Discussing a meta-analysis covering more than 100 papers on the relationship between environmental regulation and firm productivity, [Cohen and Tubb \(2018\)](#) argue that there is a greater chance of finding a negative effect at the firm or sector level, and a higher chance of finding a positive effect at the state, regional or national level. Finally, [Ambec et al. \(2013\)](#) review a sample of studies that have found conflicting results regarding the Porter hypothesis and identify a range of factors that may explain these differences. These include the variability of the regulatory approach, the firm's sector and market conditions, the environmental problem being addressed, the firm's governance and management approach, and the research methodology.

A few studies have examined the effect of environmental policies on firm performance, focusing on developing countries. For instance, [Murty and Kumar \(2003\)](#) examine the environmental regulation effect on a panel of 92 Indian firms operating in the sugar industry over the period 1996-99. Their main empirical result is that as environmental regulation and water conservation efforts intensify, the technical efficiency of firms improves. However, examining the effect of the monitoring of the Maharashtra Pollution Control Board on chemical firms around Mumbai using panel data from fifty small-to medium-scale firms over the period 2004-2006, [Dutta and Narayanan \(2011\)](#) show that the Porter Hypothesis does not hold for their sample. Other studies have focused specifically on Chinese firms. For instance, assessing the Porter hypothesis for Chinese carbon-intensive industries, [Zhao et al. \(2018\)](#) show that there is an inverted U-shaped relationship between environmental policy intensity and firm productivity. The Porter hypothesis in this case does not hold in the long run. In the same vein, [Shi and Xu \(2018\)](#) and [Huang and Liu \(2019\)](#) show that, for the most pollution-intensive indus-

tries in China, a stricter environmental policy reduces firm performance, approximated by the probability of exporting. Finally, [Efobi et al. \(2019\)](#) have focused on 842 small firms in Ghana and Nigeria and show that the effective implementation of environmental protection policies by companies substantially enhances their performance.

3 Measuring firm efficiency

Efficiency implies achieving an outcome while taking into account the resources used to achieve it, and is empirically captured by the relative distance of inefficient observations from an ideal frontier, made up of the best-performing firms in the sample ([Farrell, 1957](#)). Parametric techniques are often used in the literature to estimate efficiency, and rely on a stochastic production function — a Stochastic Frontier Analysis (SFA) — which allows distinguishing inefficiency from idiosyncratic shocks.² Since its introduction by [Aigner et al. \(1977\)](#) and [Meeusen and van Den Broeck \(1977\)](#), the SFA framework has motivated considerable research and extension. The most recent extensions include that of [Kumbhakar et al. \(2015\)](#), which allows distinguishing unobserved heterogeneity across units from inefficiency and considers both transitory and persistent technical inefficiency (see [Kumbhakar et al., 2014](#); [Colombi et al., 2014](#); [Tsionas and Kumbhakar, 2014](#); [Kumbhakar et al., 2015](#); [Filippini and Greene, 2016](#)). On the one hand, controlling for heterogeneity allows accounting for unobserved structural features specific to each unit that may explain differences in efficiency across firms. On the other hand, taking into account persistent and transitory inefficiency makes it possible to consider inefficiency resulting from structural characteristics that persist over time and that result from short-term features. In this study, we estimate firm efficiency following [Kumbhakar et al. \(2015\)](#), using as dependent variable the logarithm of total real sales for a firm i , located in the industry k , in year t and considering as inputs the logarithm of the net book value of capital and the logarithm of total permanent full-time employees, as in [Kouamé and Tapsoba \(2019\)](#). Section A (Appendix A) details our methodology for

²Non-parametric approaches, notably the Free Disposal Hull (FDH) analysis and the Data Envelopment Analysis (DEA) have been used in the literature to estimate firm efficiency. However, these methods suffer from a number of shortcomings because, as deterministic methods, they ignore measurement errors as well as any stochastic influence, considering any variation across units as inefficiency ([Kumbhakar and Lovell, 2003](#); [Fiorentino et al., 2006](#)).

estimating the efficiency scores.

4 Data

Subsections 4.1, 4.2, and 4.3 describe the main variables used in the study. Then, subsection 4.4 provides some descriptive statistics.

4.1 The World Bank Enterprise Surveys (WBES) database

Firm-level data are extracted from the World Bank Enterprise Surveys (WBES) database. The WBES collects nationally representative firm-level surveys in developing countries using a standard sampling methodology — a representative sample (stratified random sampling) — with a standard questionnaire. Stratified random sampling, along with a high-quality sampling frame, ensures that the resulting Enterprise Surveys datasets represent the universe of businesses under consideration and the subpopulations defined by the different levels of stratification. We use the standardized dataset conducted between 2006 and 2020, which has a repeated cross-section structure, consisting of aggregations of individual data from comparable surveys conducted in different periods. From available data, we retain a sample of 68 developing countries over the period 2006-2020.

4.2 Dependent and control variables

Our dependent variable, firm efficiency, is captured by a score that can range from 0 to 1 (best performance). The variable of interest, environmental stringency, ranges from 0 to 100 (total stringency) and is described in more detail in subsection 4.3. We include a series of firm-level controls, such as size, age, and ownership. Firm size is captured by an ordinal qualitative variable equal to 1 for small (less than 20 employees), 2 for medium (between 20 and 99 employees), or 3 for large firms (100 employees and over). Firm age is calculated from the year when the establishment is formally registered as a new firm. The ownership includes the share of capital owned by domestic households and firms, the government, and foreigners. At the country level, we include the inflation rate

to capture macroeconomic stability — as it has been shown that economic uncertainty undermines firm investment and productivity (e.g., see [Bloom et al., 2007](#); [Chong and Gradstein, 2009](#); [Bloom et al., 2018](#); [Bambe et al., 2022](#); [Bambe, 2023](#)) — and institutional quality. Finally, we also control for financial development, as access to credit can increase innovative and productivity-enhancing investments, reduce transaction costs, and improve capital allocation and risk management ([Chauvet and Jacolin, 2017](#)).

The inflation rate is measured by the consumer price index and is from the World Bank’s World Development Indicators (WDI) database. Institutional quality is approximated by the level of democracy and socio-economic conditions. The level of democracy is captured by the Freedom House index and ranges approximately from 0 (absolute autocratic regime) to 10 (absolute democratic regime). Socioeconomic conditions are approximated by socioeconomic pressures in society that could limit government action or fuel social discontent. This variable is taken from the International Country Risk Guide (ICRG) and ranges from 0 to 12 (best conditions). Finally, domestic credit to the private sector in GDP is used as a proxy for financial development and is from the World Bank’s WDI database.

4.3 Variable of interest

The measure of environmental policy stringency must reflect several aspects of regulation and meet a number of criteria, which is challenging. As discussed by [Brunel and Levinson \(2016\)](#), multidimensionality is an important aspect of environmental stringency. This refers to the fact that a regulatory policy may target several sectors of activity related to water, energy, or air quality, or specific actors, whether households or firms. In this study and in the specific context of developing countries, we measure environmental stringency by the environmental performance index (EPI). The EPI is a synthetic index — constructed from 40 performance indicators in 11 categories and 3 environmental policy objectives — and captures a country’s progress in improving environmental health, mitigating climate change, and protecting the vitality of ecosystems (see [Figure 1](#)). Weights are assigned to the different aspects of the measure, resulting in an EPI between 0 and 100, where higher values reflect better performance. According to the latest report

on the EPI (Wolf et al., 2022), the list of the 10 best-performing countries includes OECD countries for the most part, while the bottom ten countries include only developing economies. The EPI has been used in the literature to compare and track country performance regarding international policies — including the Sustainable Development Goals (Pimonenko et al., 2018) — or to examine the economic, political, and institutional determinants of environmental performance (Álvarez et al., 2018; Wendling et al., 2022; Zhao and Madni, 2021).

In Appendix B, we conduct a comparative analysis between the EPI and the Environmental policy stringency index (EPSI) developed by the OECD (and only available for OECD countries), by discussing the different methodologies used to calculate each indicator. In subsection B.3 (Appendix B), we compare the EPI results for OECD countries with those of the EPSI for the same countries, over 1990-2020. The Pearson correlations calculated show an overall positive relationship between the two indicators, which is significant at the 1% threshold, with a magnitude of 70%. In other words, in comparison with the EPSI which covers only OECD countries, the EPI is a relevant indicator and has the advantage of covering both advanced and developing countries. Finally, although the EPI provides a multidimensional measure of environmental stringency for a wide panel of countries, the indicator does not detail the different instruments used, as is the case for other environmental stringency indicators, such as the EPSI.

4.4 Descriptive statistics

Figure 2 displays the average evolution of firm efficiency and the environmental performance index (EPI) in the countries in our sample, over the period 2006-2020. The efficiency scores can, by construction, range from 0 to 1. In order to make the graphs easier to visualize, in this section (and only here), we plot the efficiency scores on the same scale as the EPI, so that both indices can range from 0 to 100, where higher values indicate better performance. Over our study period and sample, we report an average efficiency score of 53% and a standard deviation of about 10%, suggesting a reasonable dispersion around the sample mean. A score of 53% for a given firm means that the latter could, on average, increase its output by 47%, for the same level of inputs used.

Figure 1: EPI framework from (Wolf et al., 2022)

Notes: The 2022 EPI framework. 40 performance indicators fall into 11 issue categories, which are aggregated into three policy objectives. Weights show the percentage of the total EPI score. (Wolf et al., 2022)

This suggests that, on average, there is considerable scope for the firms in the sample to improve their efficiency. Regarding the EPI, we report an average value of 32% and a standard deviation of about 7%. Between the five-year period 2006-2010 and 2011-2015, there was a drop in both firm efficiency and environmental performance. While the decline in firm efficiency was relatively small, falling from around 54% to 52%, the deterioration in environmental performance was relatively more substantial, decreasing from around 33% to 28% (see Figure 2). Over the last two five-year periods (2011-2015 and 2016-2020), although the downward trend in efficiency has continued, it has been to a lesser extent, falling from around 52% to 51%. However, there was a significant upturn in environmental performance, from around 28% to 35%. Last, over our study period (2006-2020), we report an increase of 0.47 points in the EPI for the developing countries in our sample. Although this increase is less than that for advanced countries over the same period (1.10 points), it highlights the progress made in environmental policies in developing countries.

Last, Figure E1 (Appendix E) shows that over our study period, emerging countries report a higher average environmental performance than low-income countries, with a non-negligible difference (35% versus 32%). In addition, firms operating in emerging countries are slightly more efficient than those in low-income countries (52% versus 51%), although the overall trend is slightly downward for both groups (see Figure F1, Appendix F). Finally, these stylized facts may provide some correlational evidence linking environmental stringency and firm efficiency, but do not capture any causal relationship. In other words, they do not allow us to assess to what extent environmental stringency affects the efficiency of firms in the countries examined. Consequently, in order to identify a causal relationship, the rest of the study relies on an econometric approach.

5 Methodology

We assess the effect of environmental policy stringency on firm efficiency, using ordinary least squares. The econometric model is specified as follows:

$$Y_{i,k,j,t} = \alpha + \beta EPI_{j,t} + \eta X_{i,k,j,t} + \gamma Y_{j,t} + \mu_k + \phi_j + \psi_t + \epsilon_{i,k,j,t} \quad (1)$$

Figure 2: Trends in firm efficiency and environmental performance (2006-2020)

Notes: This figure displays the average evolution of firm efficiency and the environmental performance index (EPI) in the countries in our sample, over the period 2006-2020. Both indices can range from 0 to 100, where higher values indicate better performance.

where $Y_{i,k,j,t}$ represents the efficiency of a firm i located in the industry k , in country j , in year t . $EPI_{j,t}$ is the variable of interest, the environmental performance stringency described in subsection 4.3, and is measured at the country level. $X_{i,k,j,t}$ is a set of time-varying firm-level characteristics described in subsection 4.2, i.e., size, age, and ownership. $Y_{j,t}$ is a set of country-level variables described in subsection 4.2, i.e., inflation, the political regime, financial development, and socioeconomic conditions. μ_k , ϕ_j , and ψ_j account for industry, country, and time-fixed effects, respectively, capturing specific characteristics. Finally, $\epsilon_{i,k,j,t}$ is the idiosyncratic error term. Following Paunov and Rollo (2016), robust standard errors clustered at the country-industry-year level are applied systematically to account for the fact that the variable of interest is an aggregate variable.

6 Main results

Column [1] of Table 1 reports the main results. We find a positive and significant effect of environmental policy stringency on firm efficiency at the 1% threshold. Specifically,

a one-unit increase in environmental stringency enhances firm efficiency by 0.6 percentage points. Regarding the control variables, our baseline model suggests a positive and significant effect of firm age, financial development, and sound socioeconomic conditions on firm efficiency, while inflation is negatively associated. In our sample, the average firm efficiency is 0.53 (see Table D2). In what follows, we quantify the economic effect of our estimates. Indeed, a firm with an average efficiency of 0.53 would see its efficiency increase by about 1.13% if environmental stringency were increased by one unit. Similarly, a one-standard-deviation increase in environmental stringency is associated with a 6 percentage point increase in firm efficiency. Therefore, we can reasonably conclude that the effects obtained are both statistically and economically significant.

7 Sensitivity

This section explores the sensitivity of our results by conducting a series of robustness tests in subsection 7.1, and then examining a number of heterogeneity analyses in subsection 7.2.

7.1 Robustness

7.1.1 Additional controls

Other variables, at the firm or country level, may be relevant determinants of firm efficiency. In this case, if they are not taken into account, their omission may lead to biased estimates. Hence, we investigate the robustness of the effects obtained previously, controlling for additional variables in Columns [2]-[9] of Table 1, included cumulatively. In Column [2], we include the number of power outages experienced by the firm during the previous fiscal year, as the literature highlights the harmful impact of power outages on firm performance in developing countries (e.g., see Cole et al., 2018; Xiao et al., 2022; Guo et al., 2023). Similarly, in Column [3], we include a dummy variable equal to 1 if the firm experienced a water shortage that significantly affected its production during the previous fiscal year, and zero otherwise. In Column [4], we include the number of years of experience of the top manager in the company's sector. Column [5] considers

Table 1: Environmental stringency and firm efficiency

	[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]	[5]	[6]	[7]	[8]	[9]
Environmental stringency	0.006*** (0.002)	0.008*** (0.002)	0.008*** (0.002)	0.007*** (0.002)	0.007*** (0.002)	0.007*** (0.002)	0.007*** (0.002)	0.018*** (0.002)	0.008*** (0.003)
Firm age	3.320E-04*** (0.000)	3.479E-04*** (0.000)	3.465E-04*** (0.000)	3.754E-04*** (0.000)	3.234E-04*** (0.000)	3.192E-04*** (0.000)	3.197E-04*** (0.000)	3.196E-04*** (0.000)	3.286E-04*** (0.000)
Firm size	-0.002 (0.002)	-0.005** (0.002)	-0.005** (0.002)	-0.005** (0.002)	-0.011*** (0.002)	-0.011*** (0.002)	-0.011*** (0.002)	-0.011*** (0.002)	-0.009*** (0.002)
National share	-1.215E-04 (0.000)	-1.771E-04 (0.000)	-1.758E-04 (0.000)	-1.699E-04 (0.000)	-1.744E-04 (0.000)	-1.682E-04 (0.000)	-1.691E-04 (0.000)	-1.817E-04 (0.000)	-2.354E-04 (0.000)
Government share	-2.656E-04 (0.000)	-6.052E-04 (0.000)	-5.976E-04 (0.000)	-6.016E-04 (0.000)	-6.948E-04 (0.000)	-6.834E-04 (0.000)	-6.822E-04 (0.000)	-7.655E-04 (0.000)	-3.350E-04 (0.000)
Foreign share	1.589E-04 (0.000)	1.706E-04 (0.000)	1.719E-04 (0.000)	1.797E-04 (0.000)	1.635E-04 (0.000)	1.648E-04 (0.000)	1.643E-04 (0.000)	1.385E-04 (0.000)	7.295E-05 (0.000)
Inflation	-0.013*** (0.003)	-0.017*** (0.004)	-0.017*** (0.004)	-0.016*** (0.003)	-0.017*** (0.003)	-0.017*** (0.003)	-0.016*** (0.004)	-0.008** (0.004)	-0.024*** (0.006)
Democracy	0.007 (0.013)	0.011 (0.014)	0.010 (0.015)	0.011 (0.015)	0.011 (0.015)	0.011 (0.015)	0.011 (0.015)	0.048*** (0.010)	0.051*** (0.010)
Financial development	0.006*** (0.002)	0.007*** (0.002)	0.007*** (0.002)	0.007*** (0.002)	0.007*** (0.002)	0.007*** (0.002)	0.007*** (0.002)	0.011*** (0.002)	0.002 (0.003)
Socioeconomic conditions	0.026** (0.011)	0.044*** (0.013)	0.044*** (0.013)	0.043*** (0.012)	0.043*** (0.012)	0.043*** (0.012)	0.042*** (0.012)	0.035*** (0.010)	0.024** (0.011)
Power outages		-1.094E-05*** (0.000)	-1.098E-05*** (0.000)	-1.099E-05*** (0.000)	-1.072E-05*** (0.000)	-1.074E-05*** (0.000)	-1.075E-05*** (0.000)	-1.087E-05*** (0.000)	9.497E-05 (0.000)
Water shortages			-0.004 (0.003)	-0.005 (0.003)	-0.005 (0.003)	-0.005 (0.003)	-0.005 (0.003)	-0.006* (0.003)	-0.004 (0.003)
Experience of the top manager				3.999E-05 (0.000)	6.724E-05 (0.000)	6.635E-05 (0.000)	6.736E-05 (0.000)	3.746E-05 (0.000)	-9.512E-06 (0.000)
Website					0.028*** (0.003)	0.027*** (0.003)	0.027*** (0.003)	0.026*** (0.003)	0.027*** (0.003)
Training program					0.006** (0.003)	0.006** (0.003)	0.006** (0.003)	0.008*** (0.003)	0.008*** (0.003)
Trade globalization							-0.001 (0.002)	0.011*** (0.002)	0.008*** (0.002)
Natural resources								-0.043*** (0.004)	-0.039*** (0.004)
Economic and political reforms									
Observations	14521	7731	7731	7664	7664	7664	7664	7664	7195
Pseudo R2	0.156	0.256	0.256	0.260	0.272	0.272	0.272	0.298	0.310
Country/Industry/Year FE	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Notes: This table reports the results of the impact of environmental policy stringency on firm efficiency. The main results are reported in Column [1]. Columns [2]-[9] test the robustness of our main results, controlling for additional variables. The constant is included, but not reported in the table. * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

access to telecommunication infrastructures, captured by a dummy variable equal to 1 if the firm has its own website, and zero otherwise, as this has been shown to be an important determinant of firm performance in developing countries (Harrison et al., 2014; Chauvet and Ferry, 2021). In Column [6], we include a dummy variable equal to 1 if the firm has implemented formal employee training programs in the last fiscal year, and zero otherwise. In Column [7], we include trade globalization, as this may promote the diffusion of knowledge or technology and innovation transfers that can impact the overall efficiency and performance of domestic firms.³ In Column [8], we include natural resources, since the literature on Dutch disease suggests that natural resource booms, by generating an appreciation of the exchange rate, can contribute to penalizing the competitiveness of outward-oriented manufacturing firms, leading to a reduction in investment and a gradual decline in the manufacturing sector (e.g., see Sachs and Warner, 2001). Finally, as shown by Zhao and Madni (2021), economic reforms may also be conducive to environmental regulations, and therefore indirectly affect firm outcomes. In other words, by affecting firm performance indirectly, the effect induced by economic reforms could be confused with that induced by environmental reforms, which we are attempting to isolate here. Hence, following Zhao and Madni (2021), the last column considers an aggregate measure of economic freedom, consisting of 12 quantitative and qualitative variables divided into four sub-categories: regulatory efficiency, size of government, rule of law, and market openness.

Column [9], which combines all the additional controls in the same regression, suggests a positive and significant effect of environmental stringency on firm efficiency, with a magnitude of 0.8 percentage points. In other words, despite some minor variations, the effects obtained remain qualitatively comparable to that of the main model, supporting the robustness of our results. Regarding the new controls, the last column suggests that access to telecommunication infrastructures (website), formal training programs for employees, trade globalization, and economic reforms improve efficiency, while natural resources are negatively associated. In addition, the inclusion of the economic reform variable does not significantly affect the effect of environmental regulations, suggesting that the estimated relationship is not due to economic reforms, but rather to environ-

³Trade globalization is measured by the KOF index (Dreher, 2006; Gygli et al., 2019) ranging from 1 to 100 (higher degree of globalization).

mental regulations.

7.1.2 Are the effects trend-driven?

As discussed earlier, numerous developing countries have been implementing various measures to improve their environmental performance in recent years. Similarly, given the increasing diffusion of knowledge and technological advances — in a growing context of globalization — the performance of firms in developing countries may be driven by a trend, which may be confused with the effect induced by environmental stringency. To account for this factor, we introduce a time trend in our specification and interact it with the environmental stringency variable in Columns [1] and [2] of Table 2, respectively. The interactive term is not significant, but the environmental stringency variable (in isolation) remains positive and significant, suggesting that our results are unlikely to be driven by a spurious trend. Finally, in Columns [3]-[5], we examine whether environmental stringency has a dynamic effect on firm efficiency, by lagging the variable of interest by one, two, and three periods, respectively. We observe a positive and significant impact of environmental stringency up to two years later, although the magnitude of the effect decreases slightly compared to that of the baseline model (0.3 percentage points versus 0.6 percentage points).

7.1.3 Alternative measures of firm performance

Next, following [Albrizio et al. \(2017\)](#) and [Martínez-Zarzoso et al. \(2019\)](#), we consider alternative measures of firm performance, such as total factor productivity (TFP) and technological innovation. In the first column of Panel B (Table 3), we re-estimate our main model, considering as dependent variable total factor productivity, estimated from a trans-log production function.⁴ In Column [2], switching to a linear probability model (LPM), we examine whether the strengthening of environmental policy also affects technological innovation at the firm level. The dependent variable is a dummy equal to 1

⁴TFP is estimated from a trans-log production function, using the same inputs as those included in the estimation of efficiency scores. That is, following [Kouamé and Tapsoba \(2019\)](#), we use as dependent variable the logarithm of total real sales for a firm i , located in the industry k , in year t and consider as inputs the logarithm of the net book value of capital and the logarithm of total permanent full-time employees. The results remain robust when we consider a Cobb-Douglas production function.

Table 2: Robustness check: Are the effects trend-driven?

	[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]	[5]
Environmental stringency (EPI)	0.006*** (0.002)	0.012** (0.005)			
Trend	2.743E-06 (0.000)	7.522E-06* (0.000)			
EPI * Trend		-1.649E-07 (0.000)			
EPI (Lag. one period)			0.003** (0.002)		
EPI (Lag. two periods)				0.003* (0.002)	
EPI (Lag. three periods)					-0.002 (0.002)
Observations	14521	14521	14521	14521	14521
Pseudo R2	0.156	0.157	0.154	0.154	0.154
Fixed-effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Notes: This table reports the results of the impact of environmental policy stringency on firm efficiency. Column [1] includes a time trend in the main specification. In Column [2], we interact the time trend with the environmental stringency variable. In Columns [3]-[5], we lag the variable of interest by one, two, and three periods, respectively. All the controls of the baseline model as well as the constant are included, but not reported for the sake of space. * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

if the firm has introduced a new method or technology that has significantly improved the production process over the last three years, and zero otherwise. As technological innovation or the introduction of new production methods can take several years, we lag the variable of interest by three periods. The results suggest that environmental stringency increases factor productivity and promotes the adoption of new or improved production methods.

7.2 Heterogeneity

7.2.1 Decomposition of Environmental Policy Index

This section re-estimates the baseline model, using the decomposition of the environmental performance index, i.e., by considering the three different aspects relating to climate change, ecosystem vitality, and environmental health. Each of these dimensions, as shown in Figure 1, captures different objectives of countries' environmental efforts, ranging from climate change mitigation to biodiversity protection and air quality. The

Table 3: Environmental stringency and firm efficiency: Alternative measures and quantile regressions

Panel A: Quantile regressions	[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]	[5]
Q1	-0.071 (0.050)				
Q2		0.111** (0.045)			
Q3			0.032*** (0.010)		
Q4				0.048*** (0.014)	
Q5					0.041*** (0.014)
Observations	14521	14521	14521	14521	14521
Pseudo R2	0.1763	0.1775	0.1771	0.1772	0.177
Fixed-effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Panel B: Alternative measures			[1]	[2]	
			TFP	Innovation	
Environmental policy stringency			0.093*** (0.022)	0.022** (0.011)	
Observations			14521	17058	
Pseudo R2			0.49	0.17	
Fixed-effects			Yes	Yes	

Notes: This table reports the results of the impact of environmental policy stringency on firm efficiency. In Panel A, we consider dummy variables equal to one if the environmental stringency index is higher than the first, second, third, fourth, and fifth quartile, respectively, and 0 otherwise. Panel B considers alternative measures of firm performance. In Column [1], we use as dependent variable total factor productivity (TFP), estimated from a trans-log production function and using the same inputs as those included in the estimation of efficiency scores. That is, following [Kouamé and Tapsoba \(2019\)](#), we use as dependent variable the logarithm of total real sales for a firm i , located in the industry k , in year t and consider as inputs the logarithm of the net book value of capital and the logarithm of total permanent full-time employees. In Column [2], the dependent variable is a dummy equal to 1 if the firm has introduced a new method or technology that has significantly improved the production process over the last three years, and zero otherwise. Column [2] is estimated from a linear probability model (LPM). All the controls of the baseline model as well as the constant are included, but not reported for the sake of space. * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

results reported in [Table 4](#) suggest that the beneficial effect of environmental stringency on firm efficiency is mainly due to policies targeting climate change and environmental health issues.

7.2.2 Quantile regressions

One may expect that the effect of environmental stringency on firm efficiency will depend on the intensity of regulation. Hence, in Panel A of [Table 3](#), we consider dummy variables equal to 1 if the environmental stringency index is higher than the first, second, third, fourth, and fifth quartile, respectively, and zero otherwise. As the coefficient on the first quartile (Q1) is not significant, this result suggests that environmental policies do

Table 4: Heterogeneity: Decomposition of EPI

	[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]
	Aggregate EPI	Climate change	Environmental health	Ecosystem vitality
	0.006*** (0.002)	0.0094*** (0.00)	0.0479** (0.024)	-0.0067 (0.005)
Observations	14521	14521	14521	14521
Pseudo R2	0.156	0.1802	0.1764	0.1761
Fixed-effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Notes: This table reports the results of the impact of environmental stringency on firm efficiency, by considering different components of the overall index. All the controls of the baseline model as well as the constant are included, but not reported for the sake of space. * $p < 0.1$, ** $p < 0.05$, *** $p < 0.01$

not have a significant effect on firm efficiency for low levels of environmental stringency (around 26%), the effect becomes significant from the second quartile (Q2), around 32%. Furthermore, the effect of environmental policies on firm efficiency is highest for levels of environmental stringency between the second and third quartiles, i.e., approximately between 32% and 36%.

7.2.3 Exploring conditional effects

Last, we examine whether some factors affect the relationship we highlighted above. To do so, we consider our main model, to which we add some interactive terms. Among the potential sources of heterogeneity, we consider firm size, export status, ownership, the institutional environment, and pollution intensity. In Columns [1]-[3] of Table 5, we study the effect of environmental stringency on efficiency, for small, medium, and large firms, respectively. In all three cases, the results suggest that environmental stringency significantly improves firm efficiency. However, for small firms, the positive effect of environmental stringency is slightly attenuated (Column [1]), while it is slightly amplified for medium-sized firms (Column [2]). In Column [4], we interact the variable of interest with a binary equal to 1 if the firm exports its production abroad, and zero otherwise. The coefficient on the variable of interest remains positive and significant, while the coefficient on the interactive term is not significant, suggesting that the effect of environmental stringency on firm efficiency does not depend on their exporting activity. In Columns [5] and [6], we examine whether the effect of environmental stringency is affected by firm ownership, considering the share of domestic and foreigners, respectively. No heterogeneity seems to emerge regarding these factors. Columns [7]

and [8] explore the role of institutional factors, considering the Worldwide Governance Indicators (WGI)'s indices of voice and accountability and political stability, respectively. The voice and accountability variable captures to what extent the citizens of a country are able to participate in the choice of their government, as well as freedom of expression, freedom of association, and freedom of the media. Political stability measures perceptions of the likelihood of political instability and/or politically motivated violence, including terrorism. The results suggest that better institutions amplify the beneficial effect of environmental stringency on firm efficiency. Finally, one may question whether the most polluting firms react differently to environmental regulations than others. Therefore, in Column [9], we interact the environmental stringency variable with a dummy variable equal to 1 if the firm has (potentially) a high pollution activity, and zero otherwise.⁵ The results suggest that environmental stringency increases greater efficiency for pollution-intensive firms. This result is in line with [Jefferson et al. \(2013\)](#), who, in the case of China, find that the implementation of a stricter environmental regulation policy improves the industrial performance of pollution-intensive firms.

⁵The list of potentially highly polluting firms includes mining, motor vehicles, petroleum products, plastics, rubber and chemicals, wood products, motor vehicles, and transport equipment.

Table 5: Environmental stringency and firm efficiency: Exploring conditional effects

	[1]	[2]	[3]	[4]	[5]	[6]	[7]	[8]	[9]
Environmental stringency (EPI)	0.007*** (0.002)	0.006*** (0.002)	0.006*** (0.002)	0.006*** (0.002)	0.006*** (0.002)	0.006*** (0.002)	0.004*** (0.001)	0.009*** (0.002)	0.006*** (0.002)
EPI * Small firm	-0.001*** (0.000)								
EPI * Medium firm		0.001** (0.000)							
EPI * Large firm			1.061E-04 (0.000)						
EPI * Export status				-1.602E-04 (0.000)					
EPI * National share					6.58E-06 (0.000)				
EPI * Foreign share						-1.72E-06 (0.000)			
EPI * Voice and accountability							0.044*** (0.004)		
EPI * Political stability								0.009*** (0.002)	
EPI * Pollution-intensive firms									0.002*** (0.001)
Observations	14521	14521	14521	14521	14521	14521	14521	14521	14521
Pseudo R2	0.180	0.179	0.178	0.184	0.179	0.179	0.197	0.182	0.179
Fixed-effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Notes: This table reports the results of the heterogeneity effects of the impact of environmental stringency on firm efficiency. The equation is estimated by considering the main model augmented by the interactive term. Vector X variables in isolation (without interaction with environmental stringency) and controls are included but not reported for the sake of space. The constant is included, but not reported in the table. * p < 0.1, ** p < 0.05, *** p < 0.01

8 Conclusions and policy implications

In response to the environmental challenges they face, developing countries are increasingly adopting environmental policies to reduce pollution and their impact on biodiversity. Consequently, one may wonder how such policies shape firm outcomes in these economies. Indeed, the so-called Porter hypothesis, which states that well-designed environmental regulations may improve — rather than reduce — firm performance, has been widely documented in the literature. However, so far there has been very little research on developing countries, due in part to the difficulty of measuring environmental stringency accurately and in a way that allows for international comparisons among countries. Against this background, relying on the newly published Environmental Performance Index (EPI) and firm-level data from the World Bank Enterprise Surveys (WBES) database, we examine the Porter hypothesis on a large sample of 68 developing countries over 2006-2020. The EPI offers the possibility of measuring the stringency of environmental regulation for a large panel of countries, while addressing the multidimensional nature of environmental policies. Our dependent variable — firm efficiency — is estimated from a Stochastic Frontier Analysis (SFA) referring to [Kumbhakar et al. \(2015\)](#), which allows us to take into account unobserved heterogeneity across units and provides a further decomposition of inefficiency, distinguishing between persistent and transitory inefficiency.

We draw some main conclusions from these data, which are summarized in the following lines. There is evidence that a tightening of environmental policies has a positive effect on firm efficiency, and that the effects are statistically and economically significant and robust. In addition, environmental stringency increases factor productivity and promotes the adoption of new or improved production methods. Furthermore, we conduct a series of heterogeneity analyses and draw some additional results. First, a decomposition of the environmental regulation index suggests that the beneficial effect of environmental stringency on firm efficiency is mainly due to policies targeting climate change and environmental health issues. Second, environmental policies do not have a significant effect on firm efficiency for low levels of environmental stringency, the effect becomes significant from the second quartile — around 32% — with the highest efficiency for

levels of environmental stringency between the second and third quartiles, i.e., approximately between 32% and 36%. Third, for small firms, the positive effect of environmental stringency is slightly attenuated, while it is slightly amplified for medium-sized firms. Fourth, sound institutions amplify the beneficial effect of environmental stringency on firm efficiency. Finally, we also find evidence that environmental stringency increases greater efficiency for pollution-intensive firms.

This study supports the Porter hypothesis in the case of developing countries, suggesting that environmental regulations in these countries do not have harmful effects on firms' activities, but rather are an effective way to enhance their performance. In other words, the key implication of this study is that objectives aimed at promoting environmental policies in developing countries seem entirely compatible with those aimed at promoting the private sector's contribution to the development goals.

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Appendix A Empirical methodology for estimating firm efficiency

This section describes the methodology used to estimate firm efficiency following [Kumbhakar et al. \(2015\)](#).⁶ We rely on a transcendental logarithmic (trans-log) function, as this approach offers a greater degree of flexibility in accommodating different underlying production functions, compared to the Cobb-Douglass function. The equation is specified as follows:

$$Y_{i,k,j,t} = \alpha_0^* + f(x_{i,k,j,t}; \beta) + v_{i,k,j,t} - u_{i,k,j,t}^* - \eta_{i,k,j}^* \quad (2)$$

where:

$$\alpha_0^* = \alpha_0 - E(\eta_{i,k,j}) - E(u_{i,k,j,t}) \quad (2.a)$$

$$u_{i,k,j,t}^* = u_{i,k,j,t} - E(u_{i,k,j,t}) \quad (2.b)$$

$$\eta_{i,k,j}^* = \eta_{i,k,j} - E(\eta_{i,k,j}) \quad (2.c)$$

$Y_{i,k,j,t}$ represents the logarithm of total real sales for a firm i , located in the industry k , in country j , at the end of the previous fiscal year. $x_{i,k,j,t}$ is the vector of inputs, i.e., the logarithm of the net book value of capital and the logarithm of total permanent full-time employees, as in [Kouamé and Tapsoba \(2019\)](#). The model consists of three steps. First, we estimate Equation 2 using a standard random effect regression. We thus obtain consistent measure of β and predicted values of $\eta_{i,k,j}^*$ and $u_{i,k,j,t}^*$. Second, persistent technical efficiency is computed using the predicted values of $\eta_{i,k,j}^*$. Next, persistent technical inefficiency can be obtained from:

$$\eta_{i,k,j} = \text{Max}(\eta_{i,k,j}^*) - \eta_{i,k,j}^* \quad (3)$$

Finally, persistent technical inefficiency (PTE) is calculated from $\exp(-\eta_{i,k,j})$, then residual technical efficiency (RTE) is computed in the last step. To do so, we go back to the

⁶Since information on sales and costs is provided in local currencies and at nominal values, we adjust all nominal values for inflation, using the GDP deflator from the IMF's International Financial Statistics (IFS) database, and convert them to US dollars using the exchange rate variable from the WDI database.

first step and obtain the residues (i.e., $Y_{i,k,j,t} - f(x_{i,k,j,t}; \beta) + \eta_{i,k,j} = \alpha_0 + v_{i,k,j,t} - u_{i,k,j,t}$). Assuming that $v_{i,k,j,t}$ is iid, i.e., $v_{i,k,j,t} \sim N(0, \sigma_v^2)$, and $u_{i,k,j,t}$ is iid i.e., $u_{i,k,j,t} \sim N(0, \sigma^2)$, we can maximize the log-likelihood function for the next standard normal stochastic frontier model for the grouped data:

$$r_{i,k,j,t} = \alpha_0 + v_{i,k,j,t} - u_{i,k,j,t} \quad (4)$$

where $r_{i,k,j,t} = y_{i,k,j,t} - f(x_{i,k,j,t}; \beta) + \eta_{i,k,j}$. In practice, we use the estimated values of β and $\eta_{i,k,j}$ to define $r_{i,k,j,t}$. In other words, the sampling variability associated with β and $\eta_{i,k,j}$ is ignored. Using the standard boundary model on Equation 3, we obtain estimates of α_0 , σ_v^2 and σ^2 . Following Jondrow et al. (1982), we estimate residual technical inefficiency — $\hat{u}_{i,k,j,t}$ — based on the estimated residues ($v_{i,k,j,t} - u_{i,k,j,t}$). Thus, we can use $\hat{u}_{i,k,j,t}$ to calculate residual time-varying technical inefficiency defined as RTE = $\exp(-\hat{u}_{i,k,j,t})$, and then estimate the overall technical efficiency (OTE) defined as the product of PTE and RTE (OTE = PTE * RTE).

Appendix B Comparative analysis: Environmental Performance Index (EPI) and Environmental Policy Stringency Index (EPSI)

B.1 Definitions

The EPI assesses countries' environmental performance based on a series of indicators covering aspects such as air quality, water quality, biodiversity, and climate change. The index can range from 0 to 100, where higher scores indicate better environmental performance. The indicator has been used to compare the environmental performance of countries around the world, as well as to track changes in performance over time. The EPSI, on the other hand, is a composite index that measures the stringency of environmental policies in different countries. The index is calculated based on indicators such as the stringency of air and water quality standards, the use of economic instruments such as environmental taxes and subsidies, the scope of regulation of various pollution

sources, and the strength of policies aimed at tackling climate change.

B.2 Methodology

Although the EPSI and EPI are both used to evaluate environmental performance, they differ in their approach and objective. The EPI measures environmental outcomes and impacts, using indicators such as air and water quality, biodiversity, and climate change. The index captures the effectiveness of policies and actions that have already been implemented, by evaluating their outcomes. On the other hand, the EPSI measures the stringency of environmental policies in different countries, using indicators such as the level of environmental taxes, the extent of regulation of pollution sources, and the use of economic instruments aimed at addressing environmental issues. In other words, the EPSI aims to measure the strength of a country's policies and regulations, rather than their actual environmental outcomes.

B.3 Pearson correlations

This section conducts a comparative analysis between the two indicators, over the period 1990-2020. Specifically, we consider the EPI for OECD countries and compare it to the EPSI, which is also provided for these countries. As the EPI ranges from 0 to 100 while the EPSI is between 0 and 6, we standardize the latter so that it is on the same scale as the EPI (between 0 and 100). Table [B1](#) reports Pearson correlations for the two indicators, for the whole sample and over the period 1990-2020. On average, we find a positive and significant relationship at the 1% threshold between the two indicators, with a magnitude of 70%, suggesting a strong correlation between the two measures.

Table B1: Pearson coefficients

Country	Pearson coefficients	Country	Pearson coefficients
Australia	0.8139***	Italy	0.9428***
Austria	0.8607***	Japan	0.7877***
Belgium	0.9556***	Netherlands	0.8778***
Brazil	0.4723**	Norway	0.9068***
Canada	0.8822***	Portugal	0.8976***
Czech Republic	-0.6362***	Russia	0.7985***
Denmark	0.8492***	Slovakia	0.8445***
Finland	0.8549***	Slovenia	0.9228***
France	0.9252***	South Africa	0.3819
Germany	0.4944***	Spain	0.7587***
Greece	0.9747***	Switzerland	0.8786*
Hungary	0.6380***	Sweden	0.7270***
India	-0.1890	Turkey	-0.3037
Indonesia	0.6483***	United Kingdom	0.8002***
Ireland	0.9033***	United States	0.9354***
Poland	0.3632		

Notes: OECD Key Partners such as China, Brazil, India, Indonesia, and South Africa are also included in the table. ***, **, * denote significance at 1%, 5% and 10%, respectively

Appendix C Sources of variables

Table C1: Sources of variables

Variables	Nature	Sources
1. Main model variables		
Environmental Performance Index	Index ranging from 0 to 100	https://epi.yale.edu/epi-results/2022/component/epi
Firm efficiency score	Index ranging from 0 to 1	Authors, from World Bank Enterprise Survey (WBES)
Firm age	Continuous	WBES
Firm size	Multinomial	WBES
National share	Continuous	WBES
Government share	Continuous	WBES
Foreign share	Continuous	WBES
Inflation	Continuous	World Development Indicators (WDI)
Democracy	Index ranging from 0 to 10	Freedom House index
Financial development (Domestic credit to the private sector, %GDP)	Continuous	WDI
Socioeconomic conditions	Index ranging from 0 to 12	International Country Risk Guide (ICRG)
2. Additional variables		
Power outages	Continuous	WBES
Experience of the top manager	Continuous	WBES
Website	Dummy	WBES
Training program	Dummy	WBES
Natural resources	Continuous	WDI
Economic reforms	Index ranging from 0 to 100	https://www.heritage.org/index/explore
Trade globalization	KOF index ranging from 1 to 100	Dreher (2006); Gygli et al. (2019)
Total factor productivity	Continuous	Authors, from WBES
Technological innovation	Dummy	WBES

Appendix D Sample and descriptive statistics

Table D1: Sample

Angola	Argentina	Bangladesh	Benin
Bhutan	Bolivia	Brazil	Burundi
Cambodia	Cameroon	Chad	Chile
China	Colombia	Congo, Dem. Rep.	Costa Rica
Cote d'Ivoire	Croatia	Dominican Republic	Ecuador
Egypt, Arab Rep.	El Salvador	Eswatini	Ethiopia
Ghana	Guinea	Guinea-Bissau	Honduras
Indonesia	Iraq	Jamaica	Kenya
Liberia	Madagascar	Malaysia	Mali
Mauritania	Mauritius	Mexico	Mongolia
Mozambique	Myanmar	Namibia	Nepal
Nicaragua	North Macedonia	Pakistan	Papua New Guinea
Peru	Philippines	Romania	Senegal
Serbia	Sierra Leone	Solomon Islands	South Africa
South Sudan	Sri Lanka	Thailand	Timor-Leste
Togo	Trinidad and Tobago	Tunisia	Turkey
Uganda	Vietnam	Yemen, Rep.	Zambia

Table D2: Descriptive statistics of the main variables

Variable	Obs.	Mean	Sd	Min	Max
Firm efficiency	32,113	0.531	0.0998	0.009	0.893
Environmental stringency	51,995	32.164	7.306	18.356	67.507
Firm age	39,660	27.021	16.290	2	350
Firm size	51,995	1.865	0.793	1	3
National share	51,271	88.776	29.418	0	100
Government share	51,243	0.540	5.799	0	100
Foreign share	51,221	8.534	26.059	0	100
Inflation	49,901	6.970	4.542	-1.537	31.373
Democracy	35,542	7.231	2.069	1.166	10
Financial development	47,584	42.092	33.814	1.133	149.373
Socioeconomic conditions	45,267	4.789	1.771	0.5	9.583

Appendix E Trends in EPI (2006-2020): Emerging vs. Low-income countries

Figure E 1: Trends in environmental performance (EPI) in emerging and low-income countries (2006-2020)

Notes: This figure displays the average evolution of the environmental performance index (EPI) in our sample and over our study period (2006-2020), distinguishing between emerging and low-income countries. The index can range from 0 to 100, where higher values indicate better performance.

Appendix F Trends in firm efficiency (2006-2020): Emerging vs. Low-income countries

Figure F 1: Trends in firm efficiency in emerging and low-income countries (2006-2020)

Notes: This figure displays the average evolution of firm efficiency in our sample and over our study period (2006-2020), distinguishing between emerging and low-income countries. For ease of reading, the index has been scaled from 0 to 100, (higher values indicate better performance).

Appendix G Environmental performance around the world

Figure G 1: Distribution of the environmental performance index (EPI) around the world (2006-2020)

Notes: This map displays the average distribution of the environmental performance index (EPI) around the world, over our study period (2006-2020.) The index can range from 0 to 100, where higher values indicate better performance. The average score for the period is 37.